

cessda eric

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
European Research Infrastructure Consortium

Legal and ethical considerations for sharing research data: Open Science for SSH researchers

Irena Vipavc Brvar

*Slovenian Social Science Data Archives
Lead of CESSDA Training Working Group*

Open Access Week 2018, 22 – 26 October 2018

Disclaimer

The information in this presentation is based on our current interpretation of the legislation and its implications for research and the archiving of research data.

This is a very fluid area and thus changes are still possible. National legislations are still being processed.

This presentation does not constitute, or should not be construed as, legal advice and / or guidance. You should seek professional legal advice where appropriate.

Social Science Data Archives (ADP) / CESSDA

- Established in 1997
- Slovenian national data repository for social sciences
- 600 social science surveys with data in a data catalogue + 150 with metadata
- Member of [CESSDA ERIC](#)

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

16 Members +1 Observer

CESSDA Data Management Expert guide

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

[Home](#) [ABOUT](#) [NEWS & EVENTS](#) [CONTACT](#)

[TOOLS & SERVICES](#) [TRAINING](#) [DATA CATALOGUE](#)

[Home](#) / [Tools & Services](#) / [For Service Providers](#) / [Data Management Expert Guide](#)

Data Management Expert Guide

This guide is designed by European experts to help social science researchers make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. You will be guided by European experts who are - on a daily basis - busy ensuring long-term access to valuable social science datasets, available for discovery and reuse at one of the 17 CESSDA social science data archives.

cessda.eu/DMGuide

cessda eric

Chapters in the expert guide on Data Management

Local
diversity

Presentations
and exercises

Expert tips

cessda eric

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

- Implemented on 25 May 2018 in all EU countries.
- Applies to personal data and data of living persons.
- Applies to any controller or processor:
 - in the EU, who processes personal data regardless of whether the processing takes place in the EU or not
 - outside the EU if they process personal data of EU citizens
- Will be supplemented by national laws.

GDPR –implications for research

More continuity than change, however:

- GDPR has a limited flexibility, but leaves room for national supplementary provisions, including derogations, and this possibility applies especially to the field of research.
- Individuals get more rights i.e right to data portability.
- Institutions will be held more responsible for the data they hold and process –“accountability”.
- Increased fines for breaching GDPR and the misuse of personal data.
- Broad definition of scientific research.
- Privacy by design and default.
- Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).
- Code of conduct for various sectors is encouraged.
- New requirements for information to be provided to data subjects.
- New requirements for consent.
- Broad consent to certain areas of scientific research is possible.

Personal data

The GDPR defines „personal data“ as „any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person“ („data subject“) (Article 4(1)).

Identifiable natural person is defined as one „who can be identified, directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.“ ..

(Sensitive) Personal data

Art.9

What is pseudonymous data?

The handling of personal data in such a way that no individuals can be identified from the data without a “key” that allows the data to be re-identified.

- Involves removing or obscuring direct and indirect identifiers
- The key must be kept separately and secure
- Explicitly encouraged as a security measure in the GDPR
- Pseudonymised data or encrypted data are still personal data

What is Anonymous data?

- Information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or
- personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable.
- Anonymisation of data should be irrevocable, but should also be checked at regular intervals in light of new technologies.
- GDPR does not apply to anonymous data (Recital 26)

Six principles (Article 5)

Personal data must be:

- a) Processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner
- b) Collected for specific purposes and not processed further for incompatible purposes (purpose limitation) – **exemption for research/archiving purposes in accordance with art.89 (1) – further processing not incompatible with original purpose**
- c) Adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary – (Data minimisation)
- d) Accurate and where necessary up to date
- e) Kept in identifiable form no longer than necessary (Storage limitation) - **exemption for research/archiving purposes in line with art.89 (1).**
- f) Processed with appropriate security – ensure data integrity and confidentiality

The controller shall be able to demonstrate compliance - Accountability

[Source: Høgetveit Myhren, 2018](#)

cessda eric

Legal grounds for processing

All processing of personal data requires legal basis. The most common for research are:

Lawfulness of processing (Article 6):

a) consent

e) necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest

f) necessary for a legitimate interest pursued by the controller

Special categories of data (Article 9)

Prohibited unless:

a) explicit consent

e) personal data are manifestly made public by the data subject

j) necessary for archiving, scientific or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89.1 and based on Union or Member State law

Special provisions for archiving and research purposes

When in accordance with Article 89 (1):

- Further processing **is not considered to be incompatible** with the initial purposes (Article 5(1)(b)).
- Personal data **may be stored for longer periods** (Article 5 ,1 (e))
- Exemptions from data subjects' rights:
 - “right to be forgotten” (Article 17.2 (d))
 - “right to object” (Article 21.6)
 - “right to information” (Article 14.5 (a,b))
- Union and Member States may create further derogations from the data subjects' rights .

Appropriate Safeguards
Article 89 (1)

Data Subject Rights

1. The right to be informed (Article 13 or 14)
2. The right of access (Article 15)
3. The right to rectification (Article 16):
4. The right to erasure – the „right to be forgotten“ (Article 17)
5. The right to restrict processing (Article 18 and 19)
6. The right to data portability (Article 20):
7. The right to object (Article 21); and
8. Rights in relation to automated individual decision-making and profiling (Article 22).

Research Ethics

Disciplinary Code of Ethics (ASA)
National Code of Ethics – Soc. Assoc.

[European Code of Research Integrity](#)
University ([UNI-LJ](#))
Institute

Funder – H2020 / other EC projects / grants
Scientific Journal <-ethical committee approval before publishing

Ethics are an **integral part of a research project**, from the **conceptual stage** of the research proposal to the **end** of a research project.

Research Ethic
Committee

Guidelines for ensuring compliance with ethical principles in Horizon 2020 / **Main ethical principles**

1. Respecting **human dignity and integrity**
2. Ensuring **honesty and transparency** towards research subjects and, notably, getting free and informed consent (as well as assent whenever relevant)
3. Protecting **vulnerable persons**
4. Ensuring **privacy and confidentiality**
5. Promoting **justice and inclusiveness**
6. **Minimising harm and maximising benefit**
7. **Sharing the benefits** with disadvantaged populations, especially if the research is being carried out in developing countries
8. **Maximising animal welfare**, by ensuring replacement, reduction and refinement in animal research
9. Respecting and protecting the **environment and future generations**
10. Following the highest **standards of research integrity** (i.e. avoiding any kind of fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, unjustified double funding or other type of research misconduct)

Ethical Review Process

Is about helping you as a researcher to think through the ethical issues surrounding your research.

The principles of good research practice encourage you to consider the wider consequences of your research and engage with the interest of your participants.

Ethics review by a **Research Ethics Committee (REC)** is typically required when **(sensitive) personal data are being collected or when people are involved.**

The role of a REC is to protect the safety, rights and well-being of research participants and to promote ethically sound research.

Among other duties, this involves ensuring that research complies with national and international data protection laws regarding the use of personal information collected in research.

How to complete your ethics self-assessment (H2020)

“Consider that ethics issues arise in many areas of research. Apart from the obvious example, the medical field, research protocols in social sciences, ethnography, psychology, environmental studies, security research, etc. may involve the voluntary participation of research subjects and the collection of data that might be considered as personal. **You must protect your volunteers, yourself and your researcher colleagues.**

Start thinking about ethics while designing your research protocols. Don't wait until the last minute to seek advice or check requirements under national and EU law.

Your first source should always be at your institution (specialised ethics departments or ethic advisers UNI, hospital research ethics committees, data protection officers). “

Research involve human participants? (H2020, part)

Are they volunteers for social or human sci. research?	Details of recruitment, inclusion and exclusion criteria and informed consent procedures.
Are they persons unable to give informed consent (including children / minors)?	Details of your procedures for obtaining approval from the guardian / legal representative and the agreement of the children or other minors. What steps will you take to ensure that participants are not subjected to any form of coercion?
Are they vulnerable individuals or groups	Details of the type of vulnerability. Details of recruitment, inclusion and exclusion criteria and informed consent procedures. These must demonstrate appropriate efforts to ensure fully informed understanding of the implication of participants.
Are they children/ minors?	Details of the age range. What are your assent procedures and parental consent for children and other minors? What steps will you take to ensure the welfare of the child or other minor? What justification is there for involving minors?

Potential misuse of research results -> Risk assessment

Personal data (H2020 – Self-Assessment)

Does your research involve **personal data collection and/or processing**?

Does it involve the collection or processing of sensitive personal data (e.g. health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction)?

Does it involve processing of genetic information?

Does it involve tracking or observation of participants (e.g. surveillance or localization data, such as IP address, cookies etc.)?

Does your research involve further processing of **previously collected personal data ('secondary use')** (including use of pre-existing data sets or sources, merging existing data sets, sharing data with non-EU member states)?

[source](#)

Personal data – information to be provided

Details of your procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, transfer, destruction or re-use (including collection methodology (digital recording, picture, etc.), methods of storage and exchange (LAN, cloud, etc.), data structure and preservation (encryption, anonymisation, etc.), data-merging or exchange plan, commercial exploitation of data sets, etc.).

Details of your data safety procedures (protective measures to avoid unforeseen usage or disclosure, including mosaic effect, i.e. obtaining identification by merging multiple sources).

Details (documents) of data transfers to non-EU countries (type of data transferred and country to which it is transferred).

->Copies of notifications/authorisations for collecting and/or processing the personal data (if required).

->Informed Consent Forms + Information Sheets + Other consent documents (opt-in processes, etc.) (if relevant).

[source](#)

The ethical and legal sharing of data

Respect Ethical standards!!!!

Use a combination of consent, information sheet, anonymising data, gaining clarity over who owns the copyright to your data and controlling access.

Agreement & Licencing

The Recipient distributes deposited materials to final users under the [Creative Commons licenses \(v4.0\)](#).

Select one of the possible licenses:

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons **Public domain**.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons **Attribution (by)**.

default license

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons **Attribution (by) + NonCommercial (nc)**.

Informed consent is the process by which a researcher discloses appropriate information about the research so that a participant may make a voluntary, informed choice to accept or refuse to cooperate.

Consent (Article 4 and 7)

Definition: any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication from a person that affirms that his/her personal data may be processed

- **Freely given:** must be a genuine choice, be able to refuse/withdraw without consequences, not be in a dependent relationship
- **Specific:** not explained in the GDPR, but guidance from [WP29](#) (2011) - clear information on extent and consequences
- **Informed:** Content and form requirements, should be easily understood, easily accessible, clear and simple language, especially when the information is given to children
- **Active:** “opt in” -silence, pre-ticked boxes, and inactivity are not valid (Recital 32)

Informed Consent – Research (1)

To obtain informed consent in practice, researchers should:

- Inform participants about the purpose of the research;
- Discuss what will happen to their contribution (including the future archiving and sharing of their data);
- Indicate the steps that will be taken to safeguard their anonymity and confidentiality;
- Outline their right to withdraw from the research, and how to do this.

granularity

Consent for data sharing

Informed consent is an ethical requirement for most research and must be considered and implemented throughout the research lifecycle, from planning to publication to sharing.

Failure to properly address issues of consent may restrict the opportunities for initial use of data, the publishing of your results and the sharing of the data.

Overview	Written or verbal consent	Consent in surveys	Consent audio-visual data	When to seek consent
Consent forms	Consent in special cases	Research without consent	Withdrawing consent	Informing participants

SHARE ↩

[Source: Summers, 2018](#)

cessda eric

Information Sheet (Article 13 and 14)

A/ General information about the research and the collected research data

- Purpose of the research
- Type of research intervention, e.g. questionnaire, interview, etc.
- Voluntary nature of participation
- Benefits and risks of participating
- Procedures for withdrawal from the study
- Usage of the data during research, dissemination and storage, including how the information will be shared with participants and any access and benefits-sharing that may be applicable (e.g. traditional knowledge under the Nagoya protocol)
- Future publishing, archiving and reuse of the data, explaining to participants the benefits of data sharing and indicating whether research data will be deposited in a data repository, naming the organization responsible for the repository (e.g. Slovenian Social Science Data Archives, your institutional repository)
- Contact details of the researcher, with institution, funding source, how to file a complaint

Information Sheet

B/ Additional information if personal information is collected from participants (for example their name, where they live, information that can disclose their identity)

- How personal information will be processed and stored, and for how long (e.g. signed consent forms, names or email addresses in online surveys, people's visuals in video recordings)
- Procedures for maintaining confidentiality of information about the participant and information that the participant shares
- Procedures for ensuring ethical use of the data: procedures for safeguarding personal information, maintaining confidentiality and de-identifying (anonymising) data, especially in relation to data archiving and reuse

Example from SERISS (1/2)

Your privacy - safe storage and further use of the data

- We will treat all the information about you with strict confidentiality and in accordance with EUs General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national data protection laws.
- Your name and contact information will be replaced by a code. Only the national team, that collects data, will have access to the code list.
- When the survey is finished, the national team will send the data, without your name or contact details, to the Archive (NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Bergen, Norway).
- Your name and contact information will be deleted by [MM.YYYY].
- The rest of the collected data will be securely stored for an indefinite period. They are made available for use in scientific studies by researchers, students and others interested in Europeans' social attitudes.

.....

[Source: Høgetveit Myhren, 2018](#)

cessda eric

Example from SERISS (2/2)

.....

There is a slight possibility that some background information (such as citizenship, age, country of birth, occupation, ancestry and region <expand>) **may identify you**. In such cases, access will only be given to researchers after approved applications and confidentiality agreements are in place.

- The results will be published on our website in [month/year]. **We will make every effort to ensure** that no participant will be recognisable in any publications (scientific papers, website etc.) based on the study.

Ethical Arguments for Archiving Data

- » Not burden over-researched, vulnerable groups
- » Make best use of hard-to-obtain data, e.g. elites, socially excluded, over-researched
- » Extend voices of participants
- » Provide greater research transparency

By Netalloy

Source: Summers, 2018

cessda eric

Concluding remarks

- GDPR is research friendly and safeguards the interests and the needs of scientific research institutions.
- The legal bases for processing data for research purposes are largely in place, but the possibility for member states to introduce conditions for certain types of data may pose a challenge.
- Increased risk of re-identification creates a need for greater transparency to retain public trust.
- New requirements for information to be provided.
- New requirements for consent:
 - Must be able to document that consent has been given.
 - As easy to give as to withdraw.

CESSDA ERIC

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
European Research Infrastructure Consortium

Questions

[e-mail: irena.vipavc@fdv.uni-lj.si](mailto:irena.vipavc@fdv.uni-lj.si)